

Gemmological Analysis of Nanyaseik Corundum and Other Precious Gemstones from Kachin State, Northern Myanmar

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Abstract

Nanyaseik area is situated in Hpakant Township, Kachin State (Northern Myanmar). It is bounded by North Latitudes (25° 36' - 25° 43') and East Longitudes (96° 30' - 96° 36') in one inch topographic map index of 92C/10. The total areal coverage is about 130 square kilometers. The rock sequence of the study area consists of medium to high grade metamorphic rocks: marble, gneiss and intrusive igneous rocks, mainly biotite microgranite and serpentinite. Although the primary occurrences of gemstones in the area seem to be scarce, the secondary gem-bearing placers are noteworthy. All gemstone occurrences from this area are mainly recovered from secondary deposits (gravels). Gemstones are found as detrital fragments in gem-bearing soil horizons known as byones. According to the drainage characteristics of this area and its environs gem-bearing alluvium has been probably derived from northwestern and western watersheds especially at the junctions of major streams and their tributaries where local people wash the byone and extract gems. These gems include precious ruby, sapphire, (including padparadscha), spinel, tourmaline, zircon, quartz, diopside and almandine garnet. The Nanyaseik rubies are characterized by their distinctive colours. A glassy texture with excellent transparency makes the stone more attractive. In crystal forms, rubies usually have rounded corners, rhombohedrons, pinacoids and not well developed prism faces. Habitually, rhombohedral faces display coarse striations and some with pitted surfaces. Moreover, the Nanyaseik rubies have peculiar surface markings. These include deep broad rugged striations on rhombohedral faces (known as "Da-Zee-Yar" or "Kyaung-Chit-Yar") and the presence of small pits, somewhat look like "frog's skin" ("Pha-Phyaut-Kun" as local people called). These features are not observed in Mogok and Mongshu rubies. The common inclusions in Nanyaseik rubies are calcite (subhedral to rounded), dolomite, apatite, rutile and mica. Coarse rutile needles in the form of patchy silk are also present.

Key Words: Nanyaseik area, secondary deposits, Hpakant Township, byones, surface markings.

Introduction

Nanyaseik area is situated in Hpakant Township, Myitkyina District, Kachin State (Northern Myanmar). It is bounded by Latitudes 25° 36' to 25° 43' N and Longitudes 96° 30' to 96° 36' E in one inch topographic map index of 92 C/10. The total areal coverage is about 130 square kilometers of mountainous and rugged terrain (Figures 1, 2, 3).

There is a few or no insitu gemstones. So, the secondary gem-bearing placer deposits are of economic interest. Gemstone mining applies both open pit mining method and square pit mining method. Some gemstones may be released from the various softer parent rocks by weathering and then they have been transported, deposited and accumulated in the adjacent valleys and flat lowland areas. The gem materials are associated with other rock forming minerals in the gravels. The gem-bearing gravel beds are called "byone" layers in which ruby, sapphire, spinel, zircon, tourmaline, quartz, diopside and almandine garnet are found.

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Figure 1. Location Map of Nanyaseik Area

Figure 2. Satellite image of the Nanyaseik Area

Figure 3. Geomorphology of the Nanyaseik Area
(Three dimensional view)

Scope and Objectives

The present research aims to -

- (a) study the gem occurrences in Nanyaseik area,
- (b) carry out laboratory works including mineralogical studies and identification of corundum and other assorted gemstones, and
- (c) study the quality of gemstones in comparison with those of Mogok Stone Tract in the hope of gaining attention of mineralogists, gemmologists, geologists as well as gem dealers and gem collectors.

Methods of Study

Field Study

Minerals and gems sampling for detailed mineralogical and gemmological studies was conducted.

Laboratory Techniques

Identification of corundum and other precious gemstones was carried out with the aid of gemmolyte, microscope, refractometer, polariscope, spectroscope and other available gem testing instruments.

Gemmological Analysis of Corundum and Other Precious Gemstones

CORUNDUM	
Chemical composition	Al ₂ O ₃ Aluminium oxide
Crystal system and habits	Trigonal. Prismatic or tabular six-sided crystals, often with flat basal terminations. Rhombohedron faces may be developed at alternate corners. Also occurs as six-sided bipyramids with varying angles.
Cleavage	A false cleavage or 'parting' of twin planes parallel to the basal and rhombohedral faces.
Hardness	9
Specific Gravity	4
Colours and varieties	Red – ruby, blue – sapphire, orange-pink – padparadscha, other colours are called coloured sapphires, e.g. green sapphire and yellow sapphire.
Lustre	Vitreous to bright vitreous
Refractive Index	1.760 – 1.768
Birefringence	0.008 to 0.009
Optical nature	Uniaxial negative

RUBY	
Colour	Light pink-red (common), intense red or nearly pigeon's blood (rare)
Pleochroism	Strong to slight pink-red and orange-red (dichroic)
Spectrum	<p>The diagnostic chromium spectrum has a double line plus two weaker lines in the red, general absorption of the yellow and green, fine lines in the blue and general absorption of the violet. A red emission line may occur. May go red under CCF.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>
Inclusions	Fine rutile needles, termed 'silk' when numerous; 'feathers'-partly healed fractures; twin planes, zircon haloes, growth zoning and other solid (minerals).
Localities	Ruby is found in commercial quantities in many locations of Nanyaseik, the most important of which are: Manaw, Sabaw, Lakha, Warphu and Khaing Kyin Worksites.
Occurrence	Mostly in metamorphic and alluvial gem gravel deposits. Commercial production is mainly from alluvial gem gravel (placer) deposits.
Fashioning	Cabochon (See Figure 4)

Cabochon cut rubies

Natural uncut rubies

Three sets of short rutile
needle inclusions

Figure 4. Cut and uncut rubies showing their characteristic features

Distinguished Features of Nanyaseik Ruby

The ruby colours from Nanyaseik are not much variable compared to those of Mogok. The distinct colours are not more than three varieties. The common colour is pink-red, and intense red or pigeon's blood are rare.

The texture is fine in comparison with those of other localities. Nanyaseik situated close to the northern splay of the Sagaing Fault. So the metamorphic rocks are more affected by the pressure than temperature. Although the Mogok ruby is found in association with metamorphism, the formation process was reinforced by later igneous intrusions. Hence the temperature played an important role in the formation. Nanyaseik ruby is compact, transparent and smooth with glassy luster and texture.

The water worn rubies usually have rounded corners although it originally crystallized in the trigonal system. The dominant features of Nanyaseik rubies are well formed basal pinacoids and rhombohedrons having a vague prismatic habit. However, elongated prismatic crystals are rarely observed. Trapiche patterns are also found in these rubies. This pattern also found in Mongshu rubies, but it is not known to occur in Mogok rubies. Other optical properties are not different from those of Mogok and Mongshu, but the colour, texture and morphology are slightly different from each other.

The Nanyaseik rubies have peculiar surface markings. These include deep broad rugged striations on rhombohedral faces (known as “Da-Zee-Yar” or “Kyaung-Chit-Yar”) and small pits, somewhat look like “frog’s skin” (“Pha-Phyaut-Kun” as local people called) (See Figure 5). Mogok and Mongshu rubies are lacking such features.

Rough natural crystals of ruby from Nanyaseik Area

Typical “Da-Zee-Yar” features on the surface of the rough crystals of Nanyaseik rubies

Small pits, “Pha-Phyaut-Kun” on the surface of a rough crystals of Nanyaseik rubies

Figure 5. Distinguished features of Nanyaseik rubies

SAPPHIRE	
Colour	Blue, pink, orange and green
Pleochroism	Strong in varieties other than yellow. Other colours show differing shades of the body colour. Blue sapphires show blue plus green, dichroic colours.
Localities	Nanyaseik
Occurrence	Mostly from placer gravels
Fashioning	Cabochon (See Figure 6)

Sapphire crystal (rough)

Rough crystals of sapphire

Cabochon cut sapphires

Figure 6. Cut and uncut sapphires from Nanyaseik area

PADPARADSCHA	
Hardness	9
Specific Gravity	3.97 to 4.01
Colour	Orange-pink (padparadscha)
Lustre	Vitreous to bright vitreous
Refractive Index	1.761 to 1.770
Birefringence	0.009
Optical nature	Uniaxial negative
Dispersion	Low
Inclusions	Fine rutile needles, termed 'silk' when numerous; 'feathers' - partly healed fractures; twin planes, zircon haloes, colour and growth zoning.
Fashioning	Mixed cut (See Figure 7)

Padparadscha (mixed cut)

Padparadscha (rough)

Two sets of rutile needle inclusion in padparadscha

Figure 6. Cut and uncut padparadscha from Nanyaseik area

Comparative study of the corundum deposits in Myanmar is tabulated below. (See table 1)

Table (1) Comparative Study of the Corundum Deposits in Myanmar

Area	Mogok Area (Than Than Nu, 2003)	Pyinlon Area (Than Than Nu, 2003)	Möng Hsu Area (Than Than Nu, 2003)	Kyetsaung Taung- Kyaukkyi Area (Zar Oo Sann, 2010)	Nanyaseik Area (Htin Lynn Aung)
Location	128 miles northeast of Mandalay	100 miles northeast of Mogok	140 miles east of Mandalay	100 km north of Mandalay	80 km west of Myitkyina
Geologic Setting	Mogok Metamorphic Belt	Northeast extension of the Mogok Metamorphic Belt	Shan-Thai Block	Lies in the Westernmost part of the Mogok Metamorphic Belt near the Sagaing Fault	Northern splay of the Sagaing Fault
Lithology	Marble, calc-silicate, quartzite, gneiss, leucogranite, biotite-microgranite, syenite, nepheline syenite	Marble, calc-silicate, quartzite, gneiss, granite, pegmatite, syenite, leucosyenite,	Schist, phyllite, calc-silicate, quartzite, white marble	Marbles, calc-silicate rocks, biotite gneiss, skarn rocks	Marbles, gneisses, microgranite, serpentinite and sandstone
Minerals	Tremolite, sphene, forsterite, chondrodite, scapolite, phlogopite, diopside, spinel, garnet, corundum, idocrase, scapolite, rubellite	Almandite, orthoclase, sillimanite, diopside, phlogopite, wollastonite, idocrase, apatite, chondrodite, spinel, corundum	Tremolite, brucite, wollastonite, chlorite, muscovite, fluorine, green tourmaline, grossularite, staurolite	Diopside, forsterite, garnet, scapolite, tremolite, phlogopite, chondrodite, graphite, corundum, pyrite, dolomite, calcite	Phlogopite, diopside, chondrodite, graphite, mica, serpentine, actinolite, garnet, sillimanite, chlorite
Types of Metamorphic facies	Amphibolite facies	Almandite amphibolite subfacies (Regional), Pyroxene hornfels (Contact)	Staurolite-almandine subfacies, hydrothermal metamorphism	Upper amphibolite facies, pyroxene hornfels facies, retrograde metamorphism hydrothermal metasomatism	Almandine amphibolite facies (Regional), Pyroxene hornfels facies (Contact)
Modes of Occurrences	Ruby is found in white marble; in skarn rock between white marble and syenitic pegmatite; in orthoclase-ruby rock; in brecciated marble in fault zone. Sapphire is found in highly altered kaolinized rock (composition of syenite pegmatite); in syenite; in albite-sapphire rock; in leucocratic syenite pegmatite.	Ruby is found in breccia zone parallel to the regional trend of the rocks. Sapphire is found <i>in situ</i> in white crystalline marble and syenite contact rock; in leucocratic syenite pegmatite.	Ruby mineralization is found at the joint zone, in softer part of marble unit with no more dolomite content.	Ruby is found in fine-crystalline marble, in skarn rock, in feldspathic veins and dykes. Sapphire is found <i>in situ</i> in nepheline syenite, syenitic pegmatite, albite corundum rock and metasomatite.	All gemstone occurrences are mainly recovered from secondary deposits (gravels) in which corundum (mainly ruby), spinel, sapphire (padparadscha), tourmaline, zircon, quartz, diopside and garnet are found.

SPINEL	
Chemical composition	MgAl ₂ O ₄ magnesium aluminium oxide
Crystal system	Cubic
Cleavage	None. Most spinels are brittle.
Hardness	8
Specific Gravity	3.58 to 3.61
Colours and varieties	Spinel is allochromatic and exhibits a very wide range of colours, red, pink, light purple, dark green, orange-pink. Most apparently colourless stones give a very pale shade of pink or lilac. Chromium imparts a pink or red colour.
Lustre	Vitreous, bright. Some crystals have smooth surfaces with bright vitreous luster.
Refractive Index	1.715-1.720 (Single)
Inclusions	Many natural spinels contain minute octahedral crystals which may be of other varieties of spinel. Zircon haloes are also seen. Iron-stained fractures are common.
Mode of occurrence	Most gem spinels occur in alluvial deposits, together with corundum in Nanyaseik.
Fashioning	Mixed cut, brilliant cut, emerald cut (step cut) and cabochon. (See Figure 8)

0.5 ct

0.5 ct

0.3 ct

Mixed cut spinels (various colours)

0.7 ct

0.6 ct

0.3 ct

Emerald cut spinels (various colours)

Spinel cabochons
(various colours)A cluster of spinel
octahedronTiny octahedra of
magnetite inclusions
in spinel**Figure 8.** Cut and uncut spinels from Nanyaseik area

TOURMALINE	
Chemical composition	Complex boro-silicate of aluminium, magnesium, iron, calcium and alkali elements.
Crystal system and habit	Trigonal, three sided prisms; the faces of triangular prisms are often convex, resulting in a rounded triangular cross section with vertical striations.
Cleavage and fracture	Fractures frequently seen as wavy cracks in rough stones near perpendicular to the c-axis.
Hardness	7 to 7.5
Specific Gravity	3
Colour	Black and dark green
Lustre	Vitreous
Dispersion	Low
Optical effects	Chatoyancy (caused by parallel fibres or tubes)
Some distinguishing features	
Pleochroism	Strong in most stones, depending on colour and depth of colour. Some green stones show brown/green or even black/green. However, a few show no pleochroism.
Refractive Index	1.635 to 1.672
Double Refraction	0.025
Optical nature	Uniaxial negative
Inclusions	Irregular or wavy partially healed fractures and fluid inclusions.
Fashioning	Cabochon (See Figure 9)

Tourmaline crystals
(schorl)

Tourmaline cabochons
(schorl)

Fluid inclusions in tourmaline

Figure 9. Cut and uncut tourmalines from Nanyaseik area

ZIRCON	
Chemical composition	ZrSiO ₄ Zirconium silicate. Zircon may also contain minor amounts of other elements including uranium and thorium.
Crystal system and habit	Tetragonal. Crystals are prismatic, square in cross section and terminated by pyramids. Zircon also occurs as water worn pebbles.
Hardness	7.5. Zircon is brittle so that facet edges are easily damaged; chipping can occur if loose stones are allowed to rub together in a stone paper. For this reason, cut zircons are often individually wrapped in tissue paper.
Specific Gravity	4.8
Colour	Yellowish green and brown
Pleochroism	Weak, except in heat-treated blue stones whose dichroic colours are blue and colourless.
Refractive Index	1.92 to 1.99
Optical nature	Uniaxial positive, but metamict stones may be almost isotropic.
Lustre	Sub-adamantine to bright vitreous
Some distinguishing features	
Absorption Spectrum	653.5 nm and 659.0 nm in the red are diagnostic for zircon.
Birefringence	A maximum of 0.059 (high zircon) to almost none in metamict stones.
Dispersion	High
Observation	Doubling of the back facet edges (DBFE), which is often easily visible with a 10x lens. Bright luster; damaged facet edges.
Fashioning	Brilliant cut, cabochon (See Figure 10)

Zircon (brilliant cut)

Zircon (cabochon)

Doubling of back
facet edges (DBFE)Zircon inclusions
with tension haloes

Figure 10. Cut and uncut zircons from Nanyaseik area

QUARTZ	
Chemical composition	SiO ₂ Silicon dioxide (commonly known as silica).
Crystal system and habit	Trigonal. Hexagonal prismatic crystals with horizontal striations and rhombohedral sets of pyramidal terminations which usually look like hexagonal pyramids.
Cleavage	Very poor. Fracture generally conchoidal. (See Figure 11)
Hardness	7
Specific Gravity	2.65
Lustre	Vitreous
Refractive Index	Crystalline 1.544 to 1.553
Birefringence	0.009
Optical nature	Uniaxial positive

(i) Smoky quartz , (ii) and (iii) Rock crystals (nearly water worn)

Yellowish colour quartz

Figure 11. Crystal habits of uncut natural quartz

DIOPSIDE	
Chemical composition	CaMg (SiO ₃) ₂ Calcium magnesium silicate
Crystal system and habit	Monoclinic, prismatic crystals. Also occurs as water-worn pebbles.
Cleavage and fracture	Distinct prismatic; in two directions at almost 90°.
Hardness	5.5
Specific Gravity	3.3
Colour	Green to brown
Pleochroism	Weak to moderate, two shades of the body colour.
Optical nature	Biaxial positive
Lustre	Vitreous
Dispersion	Low

DIOPSIDE	
Some distinguishing features	
Refractive Index	1.675 - 1.701
Birefringence	0.026
Fashioning	Cabochon (See Figure 12)

Figure 12. Cabochon cut diopside

Almandine garnet	
Chemical composition	$\text{Fe}_3\text{Al}_2(\text{SiO}_4)_3$ Iron aluminium silicate
Colour	Purplish-red, pale to deep mauve
Hardness	7.5
Specific Gravity	3.8
Absorption Spectrum	Absorption is due to iron. Three broad bands in the yellow, green and blue-green are prominent.
Lustre	Bright vitreous
Refractive Index	1.760 – 1.790
Inclusions	Rounded or irregular crystal inclusions
Fashioning	Cabochon (See Figure 13)

Figure 13. Cabochon cut almandine garnet

**A comparison of gem occurrences of Nanyaseik and Mogok
(modified after Htay Win et al., 2004)**

	Mogok gem occurrence	Nanyaseik gem occurrence
Bed rock	Marbles and granitoid rocks	Marble, gneiss and granitoid rocks
Physiography	Rugged mountainous terrain	Opened flat plain with few barriers of localized hills and ranges
Elevation	Over 3800' above sea-level	About 550' above sea-level
Type of basin	Almost closed type	Mostly open pit (Inn Bye) method
Gem mining area	Over 12 × 5 miles	About 5 × 5 miles
Gradient	Fair to steep slope	Fair to gentle slope
Byone associated soil type	Commonly transported soils, rarely residual soils.	Generally lateritic soils
Depth of byone	Ten feet to over a few hundred feet	About four feet to under forty feet
Depth of bed rock	Very variable. A few to hundreds feet	Mostly about eighty-five feet
Lateritization	Unusual	Usually common
Karst topographic features	Fair to well developed	Not common, except Khaing Kyin Taung
Found varieties	Ruby, sapphire and many other precious stones	Mainly ruby, spinel, sapphire (padparadscha), and other precious stones

Discussion and Conclusion

All varieties from Nanyaseik area are mainly recovered from secondary deposits (gravels). These have been transported, deposited and accumulated in the adjacent valleys and flat lowland areas. Ruby, sapphire, spinel, zircon, tourmaline, quartz, garnet, diopside and other precious stones are extracted from byones (gem bearing gravels). Rubies from Nanyaseik are still one of the most popular and valuable gemstones. They are compact, transparent and smooth with glassy luster and texture. Their distinct colours are pink-red and intense red. Well formed basal pinacoids and rhombohedrons having a vague prismatic habits and trapiche patterns are dominant features of Nanyaseik rubies. They also have peculiar surface markings on rhombohedral faces. These stones commonly contain calcite, dolomite, apatite, rutile and mica inclusions. Inclusions may be well formed, corroded, or rounded crystals. Intersecting twinning planes are often seen. Owing to its good colour and texture, most of them do not need to enhance.

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